

1 **Sox2, Sox9, Sox4, Sox21, Sox8 and Sox3 lineage commitment program factors in embryonic stem**
2 **cells.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophoctoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Sox
9 homeoboxes functioning as lineage commitment factors in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.
10 The Sox homeoboxes with developmental potential included Sox2, Sox9, Sox4, Sox21, Sox8 and Sox3.

11 Citations

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